

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE METHODS IN REDUCING INTERNAL CONTROL RISKS: SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract

Background: Cases of financial fraudulence have persistently been reported in the audit systems of various financial sectors across the globe despite the promising role of Artificial Intelligence in reducing risks associated with financial audit practices. As such, an apparent gap exists in the current literature how artificial intelligence can be used to manager internal control risks. To explore the role of artificial intelligence in reducing internal control risks, a systematic review was conducted by seeking recent articles published three scholarly journal sites, including EBSCO Business Source Complete, ProQuest Central, and Wiley Online Library. Additional search also conducted on Google Scholar and reference lists of other articles to ensure a complete search. Articles published between 2019 and 2024, in English and having empirical evidence were included. Data was extracted using data abstraction table before being analysed through narrative approach for qualitative and quantitative findings. 3,447 articles were extracted from the literature search from the journal databases and other sources. However, only 10 articles found fit the set criteria and relevance. The articles' screening process summarized in the PRISMA diagram. Two thematic outcomes were noted; the significance of AI application in reducing fraud and internal control risks through different approaches such as improving auditors' efficiency, and the challenges against the successful use of AI in internal risk control, such as policy and structural barriers. Artificial intelligence is a critical tool for improving the efficiency of financial audit functions; however, requires more organizational input to overcome the inherence challenges, such as inadequate employees' knowledge and skills.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Financial Fraud, Internal Control Risks, Audit Quality; Systematic Review.

INTRODUCTION

Banks and other financial organizations are at relatively higher risks of fraud attack from external and internal threats due to the value of their operations. Traditionally, these institutions used to depend on the manual approaches and techniques, such as physical human surveillance, which faced many challenges, including extreme labour demand and high chances of inaccuracy (Hasham et al., 2019). These traditional approaches that relied on the policy regulations from authorities, which have gradually flopped in application due to the increasingly complex nature of the financial systems operations and threats (Rohilla, 2024; Al-Nsour et al, 2021). In fact, evidence shows that despite such regulations and policies, numerous cases of financial fraudulences have unceasingly been reported (Rehman & Hashim, 2019; Roszkowska, 2020). According to

the analytical view of Rehman (2022), about 47% financial organizations have incurred financial fraudulence due to ineffective control systems. This data gives a clue of how robust and modern means of guarding financial transactions is crucial.

Fraudulence cases spotted in financial organizations paint a picture of poor organizational commitment to guarding their customer trust. To curb potential threats, many financial organizations have since incorporated Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools in the recent decades, including Natural Language Processing and Graph Analytics, among others (Sambrow & Iqbal, 2022). Other AI-based technologies, such as the Teradata, Third Watch, and Riskified have effectively helped to reduce chances of fraud in the banking sector (Mohanty & Mishra, 2023). Additional pieces of evidence have confirmed that AI tools can significantly help reduce chances of fraud and maintaining internal audit for safe internal control (Umamaheswari & Valarmathi, 2023). Nevertheless, according to the analysis presented by Rehman (2022), effectiveness of the AI systems relies on the smooth incorporation, regular update and adherence to other current technological policies.

Since the adoption and use of AI still remains within the decisions of each organization; some studies have noted that many firm managers have been slow to adopt the current AI applications (Rehman, 2022). The applications of AI in the banking sector thus remains uncertain within the vast literature already published in this field. Therefore, this systematic review explores the application and role of AI in improving internal control system in the bank and financial sector.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This century has observed a progressive adoption of AI in most of the organizations globally with a view to enhancing efficiency and effectiveness. The global trends depict a steadily increase in AI integration, a move that is aimed at streamlining tasks, enhancing risk detection, increase complexity and promote fraud prevention in internal control processes of an organization (Munoko et al., 2020). Even though the move is seen by a significant number of organizations as beneficial, there are a number of challenges and complexities that cannot be wished away, including but not limited to the costs, job displacements, and legal issues pertaining to Intellectual Property and AI governance and regulations (Metawa et al., 2022). AI adoption in internal control system harnesses the power of higher algorithm and machine learning technology in order to streamline performance evaluation, and monitoring leading to safety, efficiency and reliability in all organization's operations (Davenport and Ronanaki, 2018).

Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (2024, para 1) defined AI as “an interdisciplinary field of computer science that aims to design and train systems capable of performing tasks that would typically require human intelligence”. About two-thirds of organizations which have already adopted AI in daily operations of business admit that AI technology is a critical component, especially in accounting and auditing fields (Deloitte, 2019). According to Haefner et al. (2023), a significant number of companies in China and United States of America realized a rapid market growth and are

progressively investing in AI technologies and reaping huge benefits. More than half of organizations which for the past two years adopted the AI technology show optimism and willingness to scale up AI technology investment by more than 10 per cent. Quest et al. (2018), even though AI tools have led to staff lay off, it has however, enabled companies to file as much as 20 times of fraud alerts. AI has enabled huge companies such as PayPal to cut their false alert by nearly half while enabling Royal Bank of Scotland to save up to US\$ 9 million through the use of Vocalink Analytics AI tool that could scan customers' vouchers and identify fake ones (Quest et al., 2018).

According to Ikhsan et al. (2022), Indonesia, Malaysia, China and Australia registered the highest rate of fraud cases in 2022 which could be reduced if data analytics fraud detection model is used applied along other supportive auditing methods. For example, in their findings, Ikhsan et al. (2022), identified that a combination of Beneish-M Score with Logistic regression data mining methods have better chances of fraud detection of up to 77 percent in accuracy.

A combination of AI technologies is deemed to yield better results in reducing internal control risks leading to internal control system quality (Monteiro and Cepeda, 2021). A variety of AI technologies such as machine learning, deep learning, natural language processing and computer vision are essential in reducing internal control risks (Deloitte, 2019; Ikhsan et al., 2022; Niu et al., 2021).

Machine Learning

Deloitte (2019), machine learning tool refers to a process of enabling computers to analyze data, recognize hidden patterns, classification of data and predict future outcomes. According to Deloitte (2019), 51 percent of the respondents they engaged uses machine learning to control risks and frauds internally, which is higher as compare to Gartner (2023) which reported a paltry 20 percent of strategists using machine learning or natural language processing in internal control risk.

Deep Learning

Deep learning, also known as deep neural network (DNN), has been used in organizations to identify high-level and abstract data features from raw data (Sun, 2019). Sun (2019) reports that DNN has led to a breakthrough in reducing internal control risks within the organizations which has adopted its use, by enabling auditors to shift from manual handling of data to automation of structured and or semi-structured tasks which includes assessment of inventories, drafting audit reports and processing of paper work.

In addition, as observed by Gartner (2023), DNN has made it simpler by providing auditors with a way to support audit decisions for unstructured audit tasks. According to Gholami et al. (2023), DNN has the potential of scanning and automatically linking financial records to their related evidences i.e. sales invoices, audit working papers and sipping documents, positively impacting on reducing internal control risks and real-time fraud detection. Additionally, it can provide a list of risky items and recommendations to be considered by the organization (Fombellida et al., 2020).

National Language Processing

The third component of AI that is applied by a significant number of organizations is the National Language Processing (NLP), defined by El-Shamy (2023) as “NLP is a branch of artificial intelligence (AI) that focuses on the interaction between computers and human language”, with Deloitte (2019) defining it as “NLP is the ability to extract or generate meaning and intent from text in a readable, stylistically natural, and grammatically correct form”. According to El-Shamy (2023), NLP plays a significant role in analyzing unstructured data which enhances the organizations’ ability to make informed decisions necessary for internal control risk and projects that by 2050, about 30 percent of NLP AI tool application will be implemented in financial institutions i.e. banking and insurance services. About 50 percent of respondents acknowledged the use of computer vision such as log in via facial recognition to enhance authentication and security (Deloitte, 2019).

Organizations face enormous challenges in implementing artificial intelligence to reduce internal control risks (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2024). According to Quest et al. (2019), integration of AI technology in mitigating and monitoring internal risks poses a lot of efficiency in management, nonetheless, these organizations have to deal with the top three challenges involving data issues, implementation struggles, measuring the value of AI implementations and cost. Approximately 43 percent of respondents allays major or extreme concerns about potential risk associated with use of AI (Deloitte, 2019). Implementation of AI in reducing internal control risk raises ethical risks because of lack of lack if integrating human values into the various AI tools. Ikhsan et al. (2022), there is need for organizations to be responsible for AI integration with consideration to data privacy and security. Integration of AI must comply with the regulations about data protection to safeguard confidential information (Rath, 2021). Moreover, additional training to acquire a level of technical proficiency is necessary to facilitate integration of AI and to be able to extract value from it (Quest et al. 2018; Ikhsan et al. 2022), and this may be an expensive venture for small organizations. As further observed by Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (2024), addressing these challenges demands for a concerted effort and comprehensive approach that put into consideration ethical issues, strategic management issues and organizational dynamics in order to achieve a reduction in internal control risks.

METHODOLOGY

This systematic review will explore and seek both quantitative and qualitative evidence in the literature to describe the significance of AI application on internal control risks. Systematic reviews often follow methodological protocols that descend from a precisely formulated research question and culminates at an overall evidence-based conclusion. Accordingly, in this case, the research is: what is the role of artificial intelligence methods used in reducing internal control risks? From this research question, three thematic concepts can be noted, including the adoption and application of AI in reducing internal

control risks and fraud detection/prevention, the various kinds of AI applied and challenges faced by the organizations using such AI tools.

Nevertheless, the literature search was be guided by specific keywords; ‘Artificial Intelligence’ OR ‘AI’ OR ‘Natural Language Processing’ AND ‘Internal Control’ AND ‘Risk Reduction’ OR ‘Fraud Detection’ OR ‘Fraud Prevention’. The two Boolean operators will help to refine the search. However, other search techniques, such as use of truncation, wildcards, and phrase searching also helped to refine the search (Kabir et al., 2023). The articles used in this review were sought from three journal databases, including EBSCO Business Source Complete, ProQuest Central, and Wiley Online Library. However, additional search was also done manually on the reference lists of other articles as well as on Google advanced search and Google Scholar. The articles search process was summarized in the PRISMA diagram (Figure 1).

The articles were scrutinized for quality before proceeding to data extraction and analysis. Accordingly, quality assessment of the articles was done using two tools, the critical appraisal skills programme (CASP) and AXIS for qualitative and quantitative studies. The articles’ inclusion was strictly based on year of publication (between 2019 and 2024), language (English), and empirical research only. As such, older articles, and non-empirical studies were excluded from this review. Subsequently, data extraction was done using data abstraction table that has the authors, country, aim, methods, and findings (Table 1). The analysis was done using the narrative approach to incorporate the qualitative and quantitative findings.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A total of 3,447 articles were extracted from the literature search from the databases and other sources. However, upon careful scrutiny, only 10 articles were found to fit the set criteria and relevance. In the process, a total of 1261 articles were removed as duplicates and other reasons before screening at the preliminary stages. When the remaining 2186 articles we subjected to careful screening, another batch of 1812 articles were removed for being irrelevant to the topic. Lastly, another batch of 364 articles were removed for various reasons, such as not meeting the study objectives. The summary of the search process is presented in the PRISMA diagram (Figure 1).

Table 1: Data Abstraction Table

Author(s)	Country	Purpose	Methods	Results
Solaimani et al. (2020)	United Arab Emirates (UAE)	To examine the relationship between AI and corporate control	An exploratory study using interviews among 10 audit experts. Data was analyzed using qualitative content analysis.	Artificial intelligence has potential impact on audit efficiency and effectiveness for accountants and auditors by reducing workload, and improving audit operations.
Rehman and Hashim (2022)	Omani	To evaluate the relationship between	Descriptive cross-sectional survey was conducted among audit experts in Omani public	Artificial intelligence is effective in improving a support function and a governance management system within organizations. It

		internal audit function and artificial intelligence.	companies. Data was analyzed using PLS-SEM and SPSS.	improves quality of audit functions that further help to reduce potential fraud and other risks.
Rashwan and Alhelou (2022)	Palestinian government ministries	To examine the effectiveness of AI in internal audit process and risk management and control.	Descriptive study using opinion surveys among internal auditors and heads of departments.	Artificial intelligence critically improves the efficiency, quality and overall effectiveness of internal audit processes, which further help to evaluate and reduce potential financial risks, providing more support to governance system and schemes.
Saad (2022)	State of Palestine	To examine the role of artificial intelligence on audit functions, including Performance, capabilities and competence of practitioners.	Descriptive analytical study involving group of 104 auditors in the State of Palestine.	The application of artificial intelligence helps to improve quality of audit professional performance as well as the efficiency of audit. AI help to tackle complex auditing processes that would otherwise be had to handle using traditional tools.
Ajayi and Akinrinola (2023)	Nigeria	To examine the application of artificial intelligence in Nigerian commercial banks regarding audit quality	Descriptive survey involving 121 employees from selected banks.	Artificial intelligence helps to improve the quality of internal audit in commercial banks – “bringing to light valuable benefits which include real time detection, wider audit coverage, improved accuracy, and efficiency.” However, AI application meets some challenges, including internal policies and employees’ preparedness.
Steira and Bangsund (2023)	USA	To examine how artificial intelligence regulates financial reporting	Empirical research design based on secondary data analysis	Artificial Intelligence helps to strengthen the nature of annual financial reports, improving the effectiveness of management accountants and enhancing management control systems in the financial systems.
Ajaaidi et al. (2023)	Saudi Arabia	To investigate the impact of using artificial intelligence applications on the performance	Descriptive study involving surveys among representatives from 38 audit firms.	The application of artificial intelligence helps to improve performance of accountants and audit firms by reducing time, costs and efforts spent by the auditors on performing these functions.

		of accountants and audit firms		However, the effectiveness of AI is influenced by size of the firm and industry. The small and medium firms face more obstacles, including financial value, efficiency in management, and employees' capabilities.
Weber et al. (2023)	Germany	To investigate how organizational capabilities can facilitate the implementation of AI by addressing the AI-based challenges	Qualitative research approach using 25 explorative interviews with experts on AI implementation.	Artificial intelligence helps to avail necessary data for informative financial analysis and other practices. However, it is apparent that that effectiveness of AI depends on data availability.
Khailtash and Lindqvist (2022).	Sweden	To investigate the effect of AI in risk management in the banking sector.	Qualitative study using 12 interviews among audit experts.	The application of AI can lead to new risks coming up in the organization, which can be organizational or regulatory in nature. The study also found another critical challenge – "Lack of knowledge regarding both AI and security within the sector."
Pehrson and Lindstrand (2022).	Sweden	To explore practices for mitigating model life risks and implementing trustworthy AI within the credit scoring industry	A qualitative single case study approach was used.	The application of AI depends on the policy structure and flexibility of organizations. Various barriers were noted to affect the implementation of AI, including technological competency, as well as organizational culture and societal awareness.

Among the 10 studies included in this review, six research articles followed the quantitative research approaches (Ajaaidi et al., 2023; Ajayi & Akinrinola, 2023; Rashwan & Alhelou, 2022; Rehman & Hashim, 2022; Saad, 2022; Steira & Bangsund, 2023; and Weshah 2024) while the remaining four articles used qualitative methods of various designs, including case study among other designs (Khailtash & Lindqvist, 2022; Pehrson & Lindstrand, 2022; Solaimani et al., 2020; Weber et al., 2023). These studies were conducted in different regions and countries mainly in the Middle Eastern countries like UAE (Solaimani et al., 2020), Oman (Rehman & Hashim, 2022), Saudi Arabia (Ajaaidi et al., 2023), Palestine (Rashwan & Alhelou, 2022; Saad, 2022), Europe (Khailtash & Lindqvist, 2022; Pehrson & Lindstrand, 2022; Weber et al., 2023), America (Steira &

Bangsund, 2023), and Africa, particularly Nigeria (Ajayi & Akinrinola, 2023). Nevertheless, these studies exhibited good scores when in terms of quality when assesses and hence included in the study.

Figure 1: The PRISMA flow diagram

Three thematic areas were noted from the research articles included in this review; including the adoption and application of AI for reducing internal control risks and fraud and the challenges faced by organizations towards successful use of AI in internal risk control.

Adoption and application of AI for reducing internal control risks and fraud

Many researchers noted the extensive and positive application of AI in reducing internal control risks and fraud. Solaimani et al. (2020) identified that AI techniques are vital for corporate control. Almost a similar finding was noted by Rehman and Hashim (2022), who reported that AI operates to directly improve governance management system within organizations thereby reducing chances of fraud and internal control risks. Rashwan and Alhelou (2022) also noted a “significant impact [of AI] on the use of artificial intelligence

in the internal audit process on the management and evaluation of risks and regulatory systems” (p. 263). Some studies have also noted the adoption of AI in improving accountants’ performance, quality of audit, control procedures, and overall efficiency and accuracy towards minimizing errors during complex audit processes (Ajayi & Akinrinola, 2023; Aljaaidi et al., 2023; Saad, 2022; Weshah et al, 2022; and Al-Tarawneh et al, 2020)). The same result is reported by Steira and Bangsund (2023) who observed a weak but significant impact of AI in reducing internal audit efficiencies.

Challenges faced by organizations towards successful use of AI in internal risk control

Despite the tremendous benefits noted in the application of AI in the internal risk control, many other challenges have been noted that affect the full realization of its potential. As noted by Aljaaidi et al. (2023), there are many ingrained challenges in the application of AI tools in internal risk control. Solaimani et al. (2020) found out that “current AI technology is less likely to redefine auditing roles and still insufficient for developing accounting information systems” (p. 171). This observation resonates with the idea that integrating the AI systems with human contributions can lead to better outcomes. Nevertheless, Ajayi and Akinrinola (2023) also found that application of AI in the audit function suffers structural and policy challenges that directly discourages the use of AI in managing audit functions.

However, other researchers, such as Khailtash and Lindqvist (2022) observed that implementing the AI systems would introduce more risks to the organization. These researchers also noted that inadequate knowledge among the users, structural resistance from the organizational regulatory and policy formations. Similarly, Pehrson and Lindstrand (2022) also noted the idea of inadequate human knowledge and awareness, and organizational structural as significant impediments of effective use of AI systems. Nevertheless, Weber et al. (2023) express that proper project planning and design can help overcome organizational barriers.

DISCUSSION

This review provides a rather comprehensive understanding of the role of AI in reducing internal control risks and fraud in the financial sector. Even though there are several and diverse positive outcomes noted in the literature, some persistent challenges have also been noted to critically hamper the effective contributions of the AI systems. This short discussion provides comparative view of the successful application of AI alongside the notable challenges.

This study noted that the successful use of AI in mitigating internal control risks is apparent. The research studies included in this review noted that AI can help to improve audit quality, enhance audit practices and efficiency, and detect any anomaly in the financial system. This observation is critical since some scholars have also expressed that AI helps to keep track of all audit practices, forecasting on the potential fraud in future for early and informed mitigation (Ucoglu, 2020; Mardini & Alkurdi, 2021; Noor & Mansor,

2019). While many researchers and scholars have acknowledged the significance and benefits of AI in improving audit quality, some researchers, including Albawwat & Frijat (2021) have noted divergent opinions among the users of AI in running their audit functions. According to Albawwat and Frijat, some accountants do not view the AI functions as beneficial in audit. In fact, some participants from their researcher indicated that there is a wide difference between the perceived effectiveness of the AI audit functions and the practical impact it makes.

Moreover, this review noted that the AI can help to uncover hidden risks and free up some human resources. In the same way, a previous empirical research study conducted by Noor and Mansor (2019) established that AI usage in the audit practices in large organizations can significantly help to identify audit errors and act as a whistleblower to flag potential fraudulent financial practices. In fact, many other researchers have also acknowledged the significance of AI in reducing corrupt financial practices even in major government organizations (Omar et al., 2017; Othman et al., 2015).

There has been an increasing application of AI in managing financial operations over the last few decades. It is interesting to note that in the previous decade when technology was relatively struggling, the application of AI in the financial sector was not well emphasised. According to a study conducted by Omar et al. (2017), about 1% of the organizations in Malaysian leading firms ever talked about applications of AI and big data in their operations or strategies. The increasing application over the years can be attributed to the significant contributions it has made in the financial sector.

Despite the increasing usage and application, AI still meets several challenges and impediments that challenges its effectiveness. This research noted many organizational elements and employee dynamics that hinder its effective use, such as inadequate knowledge, change resistance, structural barriers, culture, and policy regulations. Indeed, these challenges spread across a large context and can critically derail the financial success of an organization. Hence, there is a need to address them. Some of the measures to address them, according to this review, include employee training, policy adjustments, and embracing a strong culture of innovation.

Regarding the concept of organizational culture that takes in innovation, many researchers, including Omar et al. (2017) have strongly asserted the need to consider the structural and cultural architecture of the organization. As such, organizations that intend to adopt the use of AI in their audit practices need to conduct preliminary assessments of their premises for suitability and adaptability. At the same time, other researchers, such as Mirzaei et al. (2022) have also acknowledged the need to train employees and auditors about the AI best practices for effective results. Nevertheless, the involvement of humans in the AI system loop is a critical. A sound human resource is crucial in adding a consideration of ethics, interpreting results and applying them in subsequent decisions.

Lastly, it is also notable that the application of AI can also lead to new risks. According to the study by Khailtash and Lindqvist (2022), the inadequate knowledge among the operators can lead to vulnerabilities that can severely derail the audit process. Hence,

the need for well-equipped human resources to provide adequate technical support services in order to keep the system running. Nevertheless, with proper knowledge in a supportive environment, AI can significantly revolutionize the internal control system and manage risks.

CONCLUSIONS

From this review, it is apparent that effective application of AI systems in a supportive environment can significantly revolutionize internal control processes of an organization; improve audit functions, enhance auditors' efficiency, and manage overall internal risks controls and fraud. However, it must be stressed that organizations must put in place the necessary infrastructure, equip their employees with the necessary knowledge, and formulate policies that would enable a smooth adoption of the AI tools. The researchers agree with (Weshah, 2021) regarding the need of qualified accounting graduated students to go in parallel with practical field needs.

The future research studies need to examine whether the success of AI application varies with different organizational sizes and test innovative ways to augment a smooth application of the AI tools in managing internal risk controls and fraud.

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